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Educating Engineers for Sustainability: understanding student differences

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1 INTRODUCTION

Our society deals with many challenges such as food security, economic growth and social inclusion, which are amongst the biggest issues facing the world today (WEF, 2016). Sustainability issues like resource security and climate change also made it into the top 10 of the biggest global challenges (WEF, 2016). Universities play an important role in educating engineers that can deal with these challenges.

Society and companies require engineers with a wide range of knowledge and competences that allows them to meet labour expectations and to venture successfully into a rapidly changing world (Guerrero, Palma and La Rosa, 2014). The profile of a good engineer should be based on the ability and willingness for learning, a solid understanding of basic natural sciences and deep knowledge of any field of technology, in addition to general human values (Palma et al. 2011 in Guerrero, Palma and La Rosa, 2014: 833). Moreover, a good engineer has to be prepared for lifelong learning and must also possess good communication and teamwork skills. Technological competencies alone are not enough in the contemporary world (Maffioli and Augusti, 2003). The need to expand engineering competences is recognised by engineering academies (e.g. (National Academy of Engineering, 2004), and engineering accreditation boards of Engineering (e.g. ABET, 2014). Sustainability education has had a strong position in this call for a renewal of engineering competences. As stressed in one of the criteria in ABET (2014:3), engineers have to gain “*the broad education necessary to understand the impact of engineering solutions in a global, economic, environmental, and societal context*”. This challenge of sustainability raises a demand for a new range of qualifications and requirements for future engineers (Haase, 2014).

Engineering often deals with its responsibilities by defining three separate stages (society is responsible for the demand of technology, the engineers create it, and society is again responsible for its application) (Mulder, 2004). In the area of their expertise, engineers have been the ones who created solutions to the challenges of mankind and their judgement has been unchallenged (de Graaff and Ravesteijn, 2001). However, sustainable development is not solely a technological problem and there is a need for engineers to be able to communicate and collaborate with other experts as well as citizens involved (Mulder, 2004). In order to deal with sustainability issues, we need to educate a new kind of engineer who is “fully aware of what is going on in society and has the skills to deal with societal aspects of technologies” (de Graaff & Ravesteijn, 2001: 420).

Sustainability demands a specific kind of learning (Segalàs, Ferrer-Balas and Mulder, 2010) and in order for individuals to be in a position to engage with sustainability-related issues, a change of perspective in education is required (Rieckmann, 2012). This is the case for the way of educating students for sustainability, but this is also the case for the way the discourse of sustainability has been interpreted in higher education. One of the problems when teaching sustainability is the dominance of traditional single discipline based subjects with universities still primarily structured along disciplinary lines (Howlett, Ferreira and Blomfield, 2016). Embedding sustainability in the curriculum poses a new challenge to the academic system (Rieckmann, 2012). If we want to bring about a paradigm shift in higher education in order to deal with the sustainability challenge, we need to understand our students better and we need

to answer the question; to what extent are engineering students prepared to enter the profession?

In general, engineering education is responding to these challenges by establishing engineering programmes with focus on sustainability that rely on sustainability sciences as core content and other, more traditional engineering domains. In an employability perspective, there should be a strong link between engineers working with environmental management and corporate social responsibility and engineers working in other departments to innovative and produce sustainable products and services.

The question is if engineering students in sustainability programmes experience themselves prepared to their profession differently, compared to engineering students in non-sustainability programmes?

We will explore this by studying to what extent differences exists between engineering students in non-sustainability programmes and engineering students in sustainability programmes in terms of preparedness, when they start their study and when they finish. Preparedness is about how well-prepared students assess themselves to be for different engineering key competences. Based on the comparative study, we will discuss potentials for cross-programme activities, which could enhance students' learning of sustainability.

2 METHODS

In this article, we use data from the PROCEED (Program of Research on Opportunities and Challenges in Engineering Education in Denmark) and PROCEED-2-WORK studies. PROCEED included a survey on all Danish engineering students who enrolled in 2010 and was extended to follow the cohort until after their graduation with data collections in 2010, 2011, 2015 and 2016 in a longitudinal study. In this article, we seek to measure students' self-assessed preparedness, with specific focus on differences in preparedness between engineering students in sustainability programmes, and engineering students in non-sustainability programmes when they enter their study and finish their study. The purpose is to point out potentials for learning outcomes from these students working together, as significant different levels of preparedness can motivate peer-learning activities.

The framework for studying engineering skills and competences was adopted from the Academic Pathways Studies of People Learning Engineering Survey (APPLES) prepared by the Centre for the Advancement of Engineering Education, US (Atman *et al.*, 2010; ABET, 2011). According to Atman *et al.* (2010), these items have been developed from the ABET criterion 3 programme outcomes list (ABET, 2011) and the National Academy of Engineering report, "The Engineer of 2020" (National Academy of Engineering, 2004).

The population in PROCEED and PROCEED-2-WORK made up 4.339 students across eight educational institutions in Denmark. The response rate in 2010 was 46% and in 2015 30%. It should however be considered that the data set from 2015 suffers from a systematic underreporting of response rate since it has not been possible to extract the approximately 25% of students who dropped out of their chosen education since 2010 from the dataset.

In order to differentiate between general and sustainability programmes, we have taken point of departure in the description of the study programmes in the online guide of all educations in Denmark (<https://www.ug.dk/>). Study programmes that explicitly mention "sustainability" in their description as part of the core profile are categorised as being sustainability programmes.

All other programmes as non-sustainability programmes. This categorisation is used as the education guide is an element for students' choice of engineering education.

The respondents in the PROCEED project for this analysis is as follows, see table 1.

Table 1. Respondents in comparable programmes

Population	<i>2010</i>	<i>2015</i>
Engineering students in sustainability programmes	73	210
Engineering students in non-sustainability programmes	1609	1084
<i>Total</i>	1682	1294

We will present data from the surveys in 2010 and 2015. 2010 is the year in which students enrolled in the study programme as first years bachelor students. This year has been chosen as this particular survey gives a measurement of the first year students' preparedness and acts as a control for already existing differences in the subpopulations. In 2015 the students were about to finish their master's degree, which gives us the most accurate measurement of the effect of the particular education they have undergone. In 2015, two additional items were added, "*Environmental impact*" and "*Social responsibility*", these items are therefore reported for 2015 and not 2010. As shown in table 1, the number of students in sustainability programmes has increased from 73 in 2010 to 210 in 2015. This can be explained by the fact that from the cohort who enrolled in 2010 a large group of students have chosen a sustainability master programme, whereas their bachelor programme has not been characterised as a sustainability programme. In table 2 we present the proportion of the students in each subpopulation who answered that they were "very well prepared" to incorporate each of the items as well as the results from Pearsons Chi-square tests of significance.

3 Results

In the following, we present results on similarities and differences between engineering students in sustainability programmes and engineering students in non-sustainability programmes in order to point to learning potentials across programmes. During the presentation, we refer to the data presented in table 2 of how well-prepared students assess themselves to be for different engineering key competences in 2010 when entering the study, and in 2015 when they are about to graduate.

For the majority of the variables, there are no significant differences between students' perception of being very well prepared (see table 2). In 2010, this goes for:

1. Engineering analysis, data analysis, conducting experiments and the use of engineering tools, i.e. items concerning specific engineering knowledge
2. Design, teamwork, creativity, communication and life-long learning, i.e. items related to process competences
3. Professionalism, business knowledge, leadership and management skills, i.e. items considering business awareness

4. Awareness of the societal context, global context, ethics and contemporary issues, i.e. contextual knowledge

Table 2: Students self-reported levels of preparedness to incorporate a selection of items while practicing as an engineer. % Very well prepared for sustainability programs and non-sustainability programs (* $p < .1$, ** $p < .05$, *** $p < .01$) (2010 $N=1562$, 2015 $N= 1145$).

Please rate how well prepared you are to incorporate each of the following items while practicing as an engineer		Test of significance 2010	Test of significance 2015	2010 - % Very well prepared		2015 - % Very well prepared	
				Non-sustainability	Sustainability	Non-sustainability	Sustainability
Engineering knowledge	Engineering analysis (theoretical understanding)			4.8%	1.5%	28.3%	27.4%
	Engineering tools (professional methods)			4.9%	2.9%	26.7%	25.1%
	Conducting experiments		*	6.5%	2.9%	21.6%	14.6%
	Data analysis			5.1%	2.9%	24.6%	26.4%
Process competences	Communication			9.7%	4.3%	16.5%	16.2%
	Creativity			15.0%	15.9%	20.4%	17.7%
	Life-long learning			12.0%	4.3%	20.2%	17.3%
	Design			6.6%	5.8%	14.6%	13.1%
	Teamwork			23.7%	20.3%	41.7%	47.5%
Business awareness	Management skills			5.9%	2.9%	11.4%	12.7%
	Business knowledge		**	8.2%	4.3%	12.9%	6.1%
	Leadership			8.8%	7.2%	7.4%	8.1%
	Professionalism			12.9%	10.1%	26.3%	21.2%
Contextual knowledge	Contemporary issues			4.6%	8.7%	7.5%	10.7%
	Ethics		*	8.5%	5.8%	12.9%	18.9%
	Global context			5.0%	5.8%	10.3%	14.3%
	Societal context			5.7%	7.2%	7.7%	11.8%
	Math	*	*	14.4%	5.8%	24.2%	16.2%
	Problem solving	**	*	15.5%	2.9%	44.9%	36.2%
	Science	*		8.2%	1.4%	23.2%	23.6%
	Environmental impact		***			12.9%	35.5%
	Social responsibility		*			13.1%	19.7%

In 2015, when students are about to graduate, the above picture from 2010 is rather stable, however significant differences have emerged as the sustainability students experience themselves more prepared in relation to ethics, environmental impact and social responsibility whereas the non-sustainability students experience themselves more prepared in relation to the conduct of experiments and business knowledge.

There are differences between engineering students in sustainability programmes and engineering students in non-sustainability programmes in regard to their own experience of preparedness to the future profession. The non-sustainability students experience themselves more prepared for a number of the engineering knowledge variables.

These differences occur for students within the two types of engineering programmes. This provides a solid platform for cross-program-collaboration – they are in popular terms “speaking the same language”. However, there are also some clear peer-learning potentials, as we will turn to below.

When asked about how well prepared they are to incorporate a number of items while practicing as an engineer, engineering students in sustainability programmes rate themselves significantly below engineering students in non-sustainability programmes on math and science as well as on problem-solving (see table 2). In 2015, there are still significant differences in terms of math and problem solving, but there are now also significant more students from non-sustainability programmes that assess themselves to be very well prepared to conduct experiments and incorporate business knowledge.

In another question from 2010 (see table 3), all engineering students in both sustainability programmes and non-sustainability programmes were asked to assess themselves on a number of competences in relation to their fellow students in engineering programmes. More engineering students in sustainability programmes consider themselves average or below average their fellow students considering self-confidence (social), math, science, leadership ability as well as their public speaking ability. The relatively low self-rating in terms of math and science supports the conclusion. But the significant differences in the other items also points to more general self-confidence issues.

Table 3: Students self-assessment relative to other students on selected items (only items with significant differences are presented)

	Average or below average	
	Non-sustainability programmes	Sustainability programmes
Self Confidence (social)	65,3%	86,0%
Leadership ability	63,8%	88,4%
Public speaking ability	67,3%	87,7%
Math ability	54,6%	69,9%
Science ability	51,3%	69,4%

4 Discussion and perspectives

In this paper, we show that there are differences of preparedness between engineering students in non-sustainability programmes and engineering students in sustainability programmes when they start their education and when they finish their studies under the assumption that significant different levels of preparedness can motivate peer-learning activities. The findings are based on a longitudinal empirical survey study carried out in 2010, 2011 and 2015. 4.339 engineering students from 104 different study programmes at eight Danish universities and Schools of Engineering have participated in this study.

These findings could point to learning potentials for students in sustainability programmes to work together with students from non-sustainability programmes by establishing activities across programmes. In cross-programme activities students from sustainability programmes could be important carriers in the paradigm shift to education for a sustainable development and at the same time gain from the self-confidence of students from other engineering programmes in relation to math and maybe also push sustainability science students towards a problem-solving mind-set. Sustainability problems are complex and call for analysis, but at the same time, sustainability scientist should not take a role of formulating problems for others to solve. In the same way, engineers in general have to understand sustainability problems in order to contribute with sustainable sound innovations.

The most obvious hypothesis when considering what sustainability students could teach other engineering students is of course related to what they have specifically been trained for: sustainability. However, as obvious as it might seem, there is a lack of research to reveal the actual potential for using students peer-learning across-programmes to enhance education for sustainability.

The difference in terms of social responsibility is, however, not as strong as expected. Note that as 19,7% of sustainability students rate themselves to be very well prepared in relation to social responsibility; this is also the case for 13,1% of the other students. At least for sustainability programmes it is rather surprising that only about 1 out of 5 consider themselves to be very well prepared in relation to one of the three pillars of sustainability. The same goes for ethics, where less than 20% of the students in both categories assess themselves to be very well prepared when entering the work place.

Furthermore, there are some points, which, based on the Danish context, could motivate reflection on the design of sustainability programmes. As this study shows that students from non-sustainability programmes assess themselves as more prepared to incorporate business knowledge; programme designers might ask themselves whether their sustainability programmes could be more integrated with business. Another question, based on this study could be, how the programme in fact is covering the social pillar of sustainability.

In the perspective of education change, we can point towards some potential for cross-programme activities taking place in study environments designed to foster inter-disciplinarily learning and collaboration, A problem-based learning environment, where students work in cross-programme project groups to deal with a sustainability problem that call for both disciplines is one way to go. No doubt, that the students can learn from each other across programmes – structures, however, have to be in place in order for the students to find each other and release this potential.

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